

The Finite Satisfiability Problem for PCTL is Undecidable

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ABSTRACT

We show that the problem of whether a given PCTL formula has a finite model is undecidable. The undecidability result holds even for formulae of the form $\varphi_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_{=1} \varphi_2$ where the validity of φ_1, φ_2 depends only on the states reachable in at most two transitions. Consequently, the problem of whether a given PCTL formula is valid in all finite-state Markov chains is not even semi-decidable.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Theory of computation → Modal and temporal logics.

KEYWORDS

Probabilistic Temporal Logics, Satisfiability, PCTL

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1 INTRODUCTION

Probabilistic CTL (PCTL) [16] is a temporal logic interpreted over states in discrete Markov chains. PCTL is obtained from the standard CTL (Computational Tree Logic, see, e.g., [13]) by replacing the existential/universal path quantifiers with the probabilistic operator $P(\Phi) \bowtie r$. Here, Φ is a path formula, \bowtie is a comparison such as \geq or $<$, and r is a rational numerical constant. A formula $P(\Phi) \bowtie r$ holds in a state s if the probability of all runs initiated in s satisfying Φ is \bowtie -bounded by r .

Unlike CTL and other non-probabilistic temporal logics, PCTL does not have the small model property guaranteeing the existence of a bounded-size model for every satisfiable formula. In fact, one can easily construct satisfiable PCTL formulae without *any* finite model (a simple example of such a formula is $\mathbf{G}_{>0}(\neg a \wedge \mathbf{F}_{>0} a)$; see, e.g., [7] for more details). Hence, the PCTL satisfiability problem is studied in two basic variants: (1) *finite satisfiability*, where we ask about the existence of a finite model, and (2) *general satisfiability*, where we ask about the existence of an unrestricted model.

At first glance, the finite satisfiability problem appears simpler. Let φ be a PCTL formula. The existence of a model for φ with

a *given* number of states is decidable by encoding the question into the first-order theory of the reals (see, e.g., [12]). Hence, the finite satisfiability problem is at least semi-decidable. To prove its decidability, it suffices to establish *some* computable upper bound on the number of states of a model for a finite-satisfiable formula. One is tempted to conjecture the existence of such a bound, because there is no apparent way how a finite-satisfiable PCTL formula φ can “enforce” the existence of $F(|\varphi|)$ distinct states in a model of φ , where F grows faster than every computable function (such as the Ackermann function). Despite numerous research attempts resulting in positive decidability results for various PCTL fragments (see Related work), the decidability of finite PCTL satisfiability has remained open for almost 30 years.

Our Contribution. In this paper, we show that the finite satisfiability problem for PCTL is *undecidable*. Interestingly, this result holds even for a simple PCTL fragment consisting of formulae of the form $\varphi_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_{=1} \varphi_2$, where φ_1, φ_2 contain only the path connectives \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{F}^2 ($\mathbf{X}\psi$ says that ψ holds in the next state, and $\mathbf{F}^2\psi$ says that ψ holds in a state reachable in at most two steps).

A PCTL formula φ is *finitely valid*, written $\models_f \varphi$, if φ holds in every state of every finite Markov chain. An immediate consequence of the above result is that the finite validity problem for PCTL is not even semi-decidable. Hence, there is no deductive system such that $\vdash \varphi$ iff $\models_f \varphi$.

Paper Organization. The result is obtained by constructing a formula Ψ simulating a computation of a given two-counter Minsky machine. The construction of Ψ is based on combining several novel techniques. To make the construction comprehensible, we explain these techniques gradually and proceed in three main steps.

- (1) In Section 3, we show that there exists a *fixed* PCTL formula enforcing arbitrarily large finite models just by changing numerical constants x and y in its subformulae $\mathbf{X}_{=x} a$ and $\mathbf{X}_{=y} b$. This result is perhaps interesting on its own because it reveals a specific power of probability constraints. In this part, we introduce *characteristic vectors* as a way of representing counter values, and we also show how to implement the *decrement* operation.
- (2) In Section 4, we extend the above results by constructing a formula ψ simulating the computation of a one-counter Minsky machine. The crucial new ingredient is the construction implementing the *increment* operation (due to the chosen encoding, testing the counter for zero is trivial).
- (3) Finally, in Section 5, we construct a formula Ψ simulating a two-counter Minsky machine \mathcal{M} . Technically, \mathcal{M} is first “translated” into a synchronized product of two one-counter Minsky machines \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 . Then, we use the formulae

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ψ_1 and ψ_2 constructed for \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 by the method of Section 4 and “merge” them into the formula Ψ .

In each step, we re-use the results of the previous steps, possibly after some necessary modifications. This leads to substantial simplifications at the cost of frequent references to previous sections. We compensate for this inconvenience by suggestive notation, writing the re-used formulae consistently in **boldface**. The exact semantics of this notation is explained at the beginning of Section 4 and Section 5.

Let us note that the presented results do *not* prove the undecidability of general satisfiability for PCTL. In fact, the formula Ψ of item (3) is *always* satisfiable, although the model of Ψ may require infinitely many states. This means that the finite satisfiability problem for PCTL is undecidable even for the subset of generally satisfiable PCTL formulae. Other consequences of our constructions are formulated in Section 6.

Related Work. The probabilistic extension of CTL (and also CTL^{*}) has been initially studied in its *qualitative* form, where the range of admissible probability constraints is restricted to $\{=, >, <, =, <1, >1\}$ [17, 19, 22]. Both general and finite satisfiability for qualitative PCTL are shown decidable in these works. A precise complexity classification of general and finite satisfiability for qualitative PCTL, together with a construction of (a finite description of) a model, are given in [7]. In the same paper, it is also shown that both general and finite satisfiability are undecidable when the class of admissible models is restricted to Markov chains with a k -bounded branching degree, where $k \geq 2$ is an arbitrary constant (this technique is not applicable to general Markov chains). A variant of the bounded satisfiability problem, where transition probabilities are restricted to $\{\frac{1}{2}, 1\}$, is proven NP-complete in [3].

The decidability of finite satisfiability for various quantitative PCTL fragments (with general probability constraints) is established in [10, 12, 20]. More concretely, in [10], it is shown that every formula φ of the *bounded fragment* of PCTL, where the validity of φ in a state s depends only on a bounded prefix of a run initiated in s , has a bounded-size tree model. In [20], several PCTL fragments based on **F** and **G** operators are studied. For each of these fragments, it is shown that every finite satisfiable formula has a bounded-size model where every non-bottom SCC is a singleton. In [12], a more abstract decidability result based on isolating the progress achieved along a chain of visited SCCs is presented.

The *model-checking* problem for PCTL has been studied both for finite Markov chains (see, e.g., [1, 2, 4, 18]) and for infinite Markov chains generated by probabilistic pushdown automata and their subclasses [9, 14, 15]. PCTL formulae have also been used as *objectives* in Markov decision processes (MDPs) and stochastic games, where the players controlling non-deterministic states strive to satisfy/falsify a given PCTL formula. Positive decidability results exist for finite MDPs and qualitative PCTL formulae [8]. For general PCTL and finite MDPs, the problem becomes undecidable [6].

2 PRELIMINARIES

The sets of non-negative integers, rational numbers, and real numbers are denoted by \mathbb{N} , \mathbb{Q} , and \mathbb{R} , respectively. The intervals of real numbers are written in the standard way, e.g., $[0, 1)$ is the set of all $r \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $0 \leq r < 1$.

We use $\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, \dots$ to denote the elements of $\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$. The first and the second components of \mathbf{v} are denoted by \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 , respectively.

The n -fold composition $f \circ \dots \circ f$ of a function $f : A \rightarrow A$ (where A is some set) is denoted by f^n .

2.1 The Logic PCTL

The logic PCTL [16] is obtained from the standard CTL (Computational Tree Logic [13]) by replacing the existential and universal path quantifiers with the probabilistic operator $P(\Phi) \bowtie r$, where Φ is a path formula, \bowtie is a comparison, and $r \in [0, 1]$ is a rational constant.

Definition 2.1 (PCTL). Let AP be a set of atomic propositions. The syntax of PCTL state and path formulae is defined by the following abstract syntax equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi & ::= a \mid \neg\varphi \mid \varphi_1 \wedge \varphi_2 \mid P(\Phi) \bowtie r \\ \Phi & ::= \mathbf{X}\varphi \mid \varphi_1 \mathbf{U} \varphi_2 \mid \varphi_1 \mathbf{U}^k \varphi_2 \end{aligned}$$

Here, $a \in AP$, $\bowtie \in \{\geq, >, \leq, <, =\}$, $r \in [0, 1]$ is a rational constant, and $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

The formulae *true*, *false* and the other Boolean connectives are defined using \neg and \wedge in the standard way. We also use **F** φ and **F** ^{k} φ to abbreviate the formulae *true***U** φ and *true***U** ^{k} φ , respectively. Furthermore, we often abbreviate a formula of the form $P(\Phi) \bowtie r$ by omitting P and adjoining the probability constraint directly to the topmost path operator of Φ . For example, we write $\mathbf{X}_{=1} \varphi$ instead of $P(\mathbf{X}\varphi) = 1$. We also write **G**₌₁ φ instead of **F**₌₀ $\neg\varphi$.

PCTL formulae are interpreted over Markov chains where every state s is assigned a subset $v(s) \subseteq AP$ of propositions valid in s .

Definition 2.2 (Markov chain). A Markov chain is a triple $M = (S, P, v)$, where S is a finite or countably infinite set of *states*, $P : S \times S \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a function such that $\sum_{t \in S} P(s, t) = 1$ for every $s \in S$, and $v : S \rightarrow 2^{AP}$ is a *valuation*.

For $s, t \in S$, we say that t is an *immediate successor* of s if $P(s, t) > 0$. A *path* in M is a finite sequence $w = s_0, \dots, s_n$ of states where $n \geq 0$ and $P(s_i, s_{i+1}) > 0$ for all $i < n$. We say that t is *reachable* from s if there is a path where the first and the last state is s and t , respectively.

A *run* in M is an infinite sequence $\pi = s_0, s_1, \dots$ of states such that every finite prefix of π is a path in M . We also use $\pi(i)$ to denote the state s_i of π .

For every path $w = s_0, \dots, s_n$, let $Run(w)$ be the set of all runs starting with w , and let $\mathbb{P}(Run(w)) = \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} P(s_i, s_{i+1})$. To every state s , we associate the probability space $(Run(s), \mathcal{F}_s, \mathbb{P}_s)$, where \mathcal{F}_s is the σ -field generated by all $Run(w)$ where w starts in s , and \mathbb{P}_s is the unique probability measure obtained by extending \mathbb{P} in the standard way (see, e.g., [5]).

The *validity* of a PCTL state/path formula for a given state/run of M is defined inductively as follows:

$s \models a$	iff	$a \in v(s)$,
$s \models \neg\varphi$	iff	$s \not\models \varphi$,
$s \models \varphi_1 \wedge \varphi_2$	iff	$s \models \varphi_1$ and $s \models \varphi_2$,
$s \models P(\Phi) \bowtie r$	iff	$\mathbb{P}_s(\{\pi \in \text{Run}(s) \mid \pi \models \Phi\}) \bowtie r$,
$\pi \models \mathbf{X}\varphi$	iff	$\pi(1) \models \varphi$,
$\pi \models \varphi_1 \mathbf{U} \varphi_2$	iff	there is $j \geq 0$ such that $\pi(j) \models \varphi_2$ and $\pi(i) \models \varphi_1$ for all $0 \leq i < j$,
$\pi \models \varphi_1 \mathbf{U}^k \varphi_2$	iff	there is $0 \leq j \leq k$ such that $\pi(j) \models \varphi_2$ and $\pi(i) \models \varphi_1$ for all $0 \leq i < j$.

We say that M is a *model* of φ if $s \models \varphi$ for some state s of M . The *finite PCTL satisfiability problem* is the question of whether a given PCTL formula has a model with finitely many states.

2.2 Parameterized PCTL Formulae

A *parameterized PCTL formula* is a PCTL formula where some probability constraints are replaced with *parameters* ranging over rationals in $[0, 1]$. For example, $\xi(x) \equiv \mathbf{F}_{\geq 0.6} a \wedge \mathbf{G}_{=x} \neg a$ is a parameterized PCTL formula with one parameter x . For a parameterized PCTL formula $\varphi(x_1, \dots, x_k)$ and rational constants p_1, \dots, p_k in the interval $[0, 1]$, we use $\varphi[p_1, \dots, p_k]$ to denote the PCTL formula obtained from $\varphi(x_1, \dots, x_k)$ by substituting every x_i with p_i (we say that $\varphi[p_1, \dots, p_k]$ is an *instance* of $\varphi(x_1, \dots, x_k)$). For example, $\xi[0.1]$ is the formula $\mathbf{F}_{\geq 0.6} a \wedge \mathbf{G}_{=0.1} \neg a$.

2.3 Minsky Machines

A *Minsky machine* \mathcal{M} with $k \geq 1$ counters is a finite program

$$1 : \text{Ins}_1; \dots m : \text{Ins}_m; m+1 : \text{Halt};$$

where $m \geq 1$ and every $i : \text{Ins}_i$ is a labeled instruction in one of the following forms:

- I. $i : \text{inc } c_j; \text{ goto } u;$
- II. $i : \text{if } c_j=0 \text{ then goto } u \text{ else dec } c_j; \text{ goto } u'$

Here, $j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ is a counter index and $u, u' \in \{1, \dots, m+1\}$.

A *configuration* of \mathcal{M} is a tuple (i, n_1, \dots, n_k) of non-negative integers where $1 \leq i \leq m+1$ represents the current control position and n_1, \dots, n_k represent the current counter values. A configuration (i', n'_1, \dots, n'_k) is a *successor* of a configuration (i, n_1, \dots, n_k) , written $(i, n_1, \dots, n_k) \mapsto (i', n'_1, \dots, n'_k)$, if $i \leq m$, the tuple (n'_1, \dots, n'_k) is obtained from (n_1, \dots, n_k) by performing Ins_i (note that $n'_j \neq n_j$ for at most one $j \leq k$), and i' is the target label obtained by performing Ins_i .

A configuration (i, n_1, \dots, n_k) is *reachable* if $(1, 0, \dots, 0) \mapsto^* (i, n_1, \dots, n_k)$, where \mapsto^* is the reflexive and transitive closure of \mapsto . Note that all counters are initialized to zero. We say that \mathcal{M} *halts* if there is a reachable configuration of the form $(m+1, n_1, \dots, n_k)$. Furthermore, we say that \mathcal{M} is *bounded* if the number of reachable configurations is finite. The *halting* and *boundedness* problems are undecidable even for two-counter Minsky machines¹.

¹The undecidability of the halting problem for two-counter Minsky machines is standard [23]. The undecidability of boundedness is thus trivial for three-counter Minsky machines (the third counter is used to count the instructions performed on the first two counters) and can be easily proven even for two-counter Minsky machines [21].

Observe that when the $m+1 : \text{Halt}$ instruction of \mathcal{M} is replaced with $m+1 : \text{if } c_1=0 \text{ then goto } m+1 \text{ else dec } c_1; \text{ goto } m+1$, then the original \mathcal{M} is bounded iff the modified \mathcal{M} is bounded (even if the modified \mathcal{M} never halts). Hence, the boundedness problem is undecidable even for two-counter *Minsky machines without Halt*, where all instructions are of the form I or II (the absence of *Halt* makes some of our constructions simpler).

3 A PARAMETERIZED PCTL FORMULA WITH ARBITRARILY LARGE MODELS

In this section, we prove the following result:

THEOREM 3.1. *There exists a parameterized PCTL formula $\psi(x, y)$ such that for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists an instance $\psi[c, d]$ satisfying the following:*

- every model of $\psi[c, d]$ has at least n states;
- $\psi[c, d]$ has a finite-state model with $O(n)$ states.

3.1 Constructing $\psi(x, y)$

Let us fix a rational constant q such that $\frac{3}{4} < q < 1$ and $\sqrt{4q-3} \in \mathbb{Q}$. For example, we can put $q = \frac{13}{16}$. Furthermore, we define

$$I_q = \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{4q-3}}{2}, \frac{1 + \sqrt{4q-3}}{2} \right)$$

By our choice of q , we immediately obtain that $I_q \subseteq (0, 1)$. Finally, we fix $\kappa \in (0, 1)^2$ with rational components such that $\kappa_1 \in I_q$ and $\kappa_1 + \kappa_2 \leq 1$.

The rational constants q, κ_1 , and κ_2 are used in $\psi(x, y)$ as probability constraints. The defining properties of q and I_q are explained in Lemma 3.4.

The set of atomic propositions² occurring in $\psi(x, y)$ is $A = \{a, b, c, h, r_0, r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4\}$. For every $B \subseteq A$, we use $\langle B \rangle$ to denote the formula saying that *exactly* the propositions of B are satisfied, i.e., $\langle B \rangle \equiv \bigwedge_{p \in B} p \wedge \bigwedge_{p \in A \setminus B} \neg p$. Slightly abusing our notation, we write, e.g., $\langle a, r_i \rangle$ instead of $\langle \{a, r_i\} \rangle$. Furthermore, for every $r_i \in A$, we use $S(r_i)$ to denote the “successor” proposition $r_j \in A$ such that $j = i+1 \pmod 5$. For example, $S(S(r_3)) = r_0$. Recall that S^k denotes the k -fold composition $S \circ \dots \circ S$.

We put

$$\psi(x, y) \equiv \text{Init}(x, y) \wedge \mathbf{G}_{=1} \text{Invariant}$$

where

$$\text{Init}(x, y) \equiv \langle a, r_0 \rangle \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=x} a \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=y} b$$

is a parameterized *initial condition* that has to be valid in a state s satisfying an instance of $\psi(x, y)$, and

$$\text{Invariant} \equiv \text{Fin} \vee \text{Trans} \vee \text{Free}$$

is a formula (with no parameters) that must be valid in every state reachable from s . The formula

$$\text{Free} \equiv h \wedge \bigvee_{B \subseteq A} (\langle B \rangle \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1} \langle B \rangle)$$

ensures that every reachable state t satisfying the proposition h has only immediate successors satisfying the same subset of A as t . This

²For purposes of this section, it suffices to use only three r_i propositions instead of five (this is apparent when inspecting Fig. 2). However, using five r_i 's allows us to reuse some of the constructed formulae in the next sections with only trivial modifications.

enforces that *Free* is valid in all states reachable from t (intuitively, these states are “free” in the sense that they do not require further attention).

The formula *Fin* is defined as follows:

$$\text{Fin} \equiv \bigvee_{i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}} \langle a, r_i \rangle \wedge \text{FSuc}_i \wedge \text{Zero}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FSuc}_i &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1}(\langle h, a, S(r_i) \rangle \vee \langle h, b, S^2(r_i) \rangle \vee \langle h, c, S^2(r_i) \rangle), \\ \text{Zero} &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=\kappa_1} a \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=\kappa_2} b. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we put

$$\text{Trans} \equiv \bigvee_{i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}} \langle a, r_i \rangle \wedge \text{Suc}_i \wedge \text{Interval} \wedge \text{Eq}_i$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Suc}_i &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1}(\langle a, S(r_i) \rangle \vee \langle h, b, S^2(r_i) \rangle \vee \langle h, c, S^2(r_i) \rangle) \\ \text{Interval} &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{>(1-\sqrt{4q-3})/2} a \wedge \mathbf{X}_{<(1+\sqrt{4q-3})/2} a \wedge \mathbf{X}_{>0} b \\ \text{Eq}_i &\equiv \mathbf{F}_{=q}^2 S^2(r_i) \wedge \mathbf{F}_{=q}^2((S^2(r_i) \wedge \neg b) \vee (S^3(r_i) \wedge b)) \end{aligned}$$

This completes the definition of $\psi(x, y)$.

3.2 Models of $\psi(x, y)$ instances

In this section, we formulate several simple observations that are valid for every model of every instance of $\psi(x, y)$.

We start by introducing some useful notions applicable to arbitrary Markov chains.

Definition 3.2 (characteristic vector, A_t , B_t , and C_t sets). Let t be a state of a Markov chain with transition function P . Let A_t , B_t , and C_t be the sets of all immediate successors of t satisfying the atomic propositions a , b , and c , respectively.

The *characteristic vector* of t is the vector $\mathbf{v}[t] \in [0, 1]^2$ where $\mathbf{v}[t]_1 = \sum_{u \in A_t} P(t, u)$ and $\mathbf{v}[t]_2 = \sum_{u \in B_t} P(t, u)$. Observe that $\mathbf{v}[t]_1$ and $\mathbf{v}[t]_2$ is the probability of satisfying the path formula $\mathbf{X}a$ and $\mathbf{X}b$ in t , respectively.

Let $M = (S, P, \nu)$ be a Markov chain such that $s \models \psi[c, d]$ where $s \in S$ and $\psi[c, d]$ is an instance of $\psi(x, y)$. Furthermore, assume that every $t \in S$ is reachable from s .

Note that for every $t \in S$, we have that *exactly one*³ of the following possibilities holds: $t \models \text{Free}$, $t \models \text{Fin}$, or $t \models \text{Trans}$. Thus, S is partitioned into three disjoint subsets of *free*, *final*, and *transient* states, respectively. As we shall see, our constructions crucially depend on analyzing the properties of characteristic vectors of transient states.

Properties of free states. Observe that a state t is free iff $t \models h$. The formula *Free* ensures that all immediate successors of a free state t (and consequently also all states reachable from t) satisfy the same set of atomic propositions as t .

Properties of final states. The formula *Fin* ensures that all immediate successors of every final state are free and the characteristic vector of a final state is equal to κ .

³In particular, note that assuming $t \models \text{Fin} \wedge \text{Trans}$ implies $t \models \mathbf{X}_{>0} \langle a, S(r_i) \rangle$ and $t \models \mathbf{X}_{>0} \langle h, a, S(r_i) \rangle$, hence $t \not\models \text{FSuc}_i$ and $t \not\models \text{Suc}_i$ (contradiction).

Properties of transient states. Let t be a transient state, i.e.,

$$t \models \langle a, r_i \rangle \wedge \text{Suc}_i \wedge \text{Interval} \wedge \text{Eq}_i$$

for exactly one $i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}$. The formula *Suc_i* says that t has precisely three types of immediate successors:

- I. transient or final states satisfying $\langle a, S(r_i) \rangle$,
- II. free states satisfying $\langle h, b, S^2(r_i) \rangle$,
- III. free states satisfying $\langle h, c, S^2(r_i) \rangle$.

Note that the first/second component of $\mathbf{v}[t]$ is precisely the total probability of entering an immediate successor of Type I/II from t , respectively (see Fig. 2, where u_1, \dots, u_k are Type I successors of t , and $\mathbf{v}[t]_1 = \sum_{j=1}^k P(t, u_j)$).

The formula *Interval* guarantees that $\mathbf{v}[t]_1 \in I_q$ and $\mathbf{v}[t]_2 > 0$ (i.e., $\mathbf{v}[t] \in W$, see Definition 3.3). Explaining the meaning of *Eq_i* is more complicated (see Section 3.4) and requires introducing some new notions.

3.3 Functions τ and σ

In this section, we introduce crucial concepts underpinning our results. Intuitively, we use characteristic vectors to encode non-negative integers, where κ represents zero, and decrementing/incrementing the current value corresponds to performing the functions τ/σ introduced in our next definition.

Definition 3.3 (τ , σ , and W). Let $W = I_q \times (0, \infty)$. Furthermore, let $\tau, \sigma : W \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ be functions defined as follows:

- $\tau(\mathbf{v}) = ((q-1+\mathbf{v}_1)/\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2/\mathbf{v}_1)$
- $\sigma(\mathbf{v}) = ((1-q)/(1-\mathbf{v}_1), (\mathbf{v}_2(1-q))/(1-\mathbf{v}_1))$.

The *slope* of a line or a line segment in \mathbb{R}^2 is defined in the standard way. For all $\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ where $\mathbf{v} \neq \mathbf{u}$, we use *slope*(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u}) to denote the slope of the line containing \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u} .

In the next lemma, we use the defining properties of q and I_q (this explains their purpose). The proof is obtained by straightforward calculations.

LEMMA 3.4. *For every $\mathbf{v} \in W$ we have that*

- $\tau(\mathbf{v}), \sigma(\mathbf{v}) \in W$;
- $\tau(\mathbf{v})$ is strictly larger than \mathbf{v} in both components;
- $\text{slope}(\mathbf{v}, \tau(\mathbf{v})) < \text{slope}(\tau(\mathbf{v}), \tau^2(\mathbf{v}))$;
- $\sigma(\tau(\mathbf{v})) = \tau(\sigma(\mathbf{v})) = \mathbf{v}$.

Our proof of Theorem 3.1 is based on observing that for every transient state t , the formula *Interval* \wedge *Eq_i* guarantees $\mathbf{v}[u] = \tau(\mathbf{v}[t])$ for every $u \in A_t$ (see Theorem 3.9). To prove this observation, we need several “geometric” notions.

For every $\mathbf{u} \in W$, let $L(\mathbf{u})$ be the line segment between the points \mathbf{u} and $\tau(\mathbf{u})$, including \mathbf{u} and excluding $\tau(\mathbf{u})$, i.e.,

$$L(\mathbf{u}) = \{\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid \mathbf{w} = \lambda \mathbf{u} + (1-\lambda)\tau(\mathbf{u}) \text{ for some } \lambda \in (0, 1]\}.$$

By Lemma 3.4, $L(\mathbf{u})$ has a positive slope, and the slope of $L(\tau(\mathbf{u}))$ is strictly larger than the slope of $L(\mathbf{u})$.

We use $H(\mathbf{u})$ to denote the closed half-space above the line obtained by prolonging the line segment $L(\mathbf{u})$, i.e.,

$$H(\mathbf{u}) = \{\mathbf{u} + \alpha \mid \alpha \in \mathbb{R}^2, (\tau(\mathbf{u})_2 - \mathbf{u}_2, \mathbf{u}_1 - \tau(\mathbf{u})_1) \cdot \alpha \leq 0\}.$$

Figure 1: Points(\mathbf{v}), Lines(\mathbf{v}), and Area(\mathbf{v}).

Definition 3.5. For every $\mathbf{v} \in W$, let

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Points}(\mathbf{v}) &= \{\tau^k(\mathbf{v}), \sigma^k(\mathbf{v}) \mid k \in \mathbb{N}\}, \\ \text{Lines}(\mathbf{v}) &= \bigcup_{\mathbf{u} \in \text{Points}(\mathbf{v})} L(\mathbf{u}), \\ \text{Area}(\mathbf{v}) &= W \cap \bigcap_{\mathbf{u} \in \text{Points}(\mathbf{v})} H(\mathbf{u}). \end{aligned}$$

The structure of $\text{Points}(\mathbf{v})$, $\text{Lines}(\mathbf{v})$, and $\text{Area}(\mathbf{v})$ is shown in Fig. 1.

Now, we present a sequence of technical observations culminating with (crucial) Theorem 3.9.

A convex combination of vectors $\mathbf{u}^1, \dots, \mathbf{u}^k$ is *positive* if all coefficients used in the combination are positive. The next lemma is a trivial corollary to Lemma 3.4 (cf. Fig. 1).

LEMMA 3.6. For every $\mathbf{v} \in W$ and every $\mathbf{u} \in \text{Points}(\mathbf{v})$, we have the following:

- If \mathbf{u} is a positive convex combination of $\mathbf{u}^1, \dots, \mathbf{u}^k \in \text{Area}(\mathbf{v})$, then $\mathbf{u}^1 = \dots = \mathbf{u}^k = \mathbf{u}$.
- If $\mathbf{w} \in L(\mathbf{u})$ is a positive convex combination of $\mathbf{u}^1, \dots, \mathbf{u}^k \in \text{Area}(\mathbf{v})$, then $\mathbf{u}^1, \dots, \mathbf{u}^k \in L(\mathbf{u}) \cup \{\tau(\mathbf{u})\}$.
- For every $\mathbf{w} \in W$ such that $\mathbf{w}_1 = \mathbf{v}_1$ and $\mathbf{w}_2 < \mathbf{v}_2$ we have that $\text{Area}(\mathbf{v}) \subset \text{Area}(\mathbf{w})$.

LEMMA 3.7. For every $\mathbf{u} \in W \setminus \text{Area}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$, there exists $\boldsymbol{\mu}[\mathbf{u}] \in W$ such that $\boldsymbol{\mu}[\mathbf{u}]_1 = \boldsymbol{\kappa}_1$, $\boldsymbol{\mu}[\mathbf{u}]_2 < \boldsymbol{\kappa}_2$, and $\mathbf{u} \in \text{Lines}(\boldsymbol{\mu}[\mathbf{u}])$.

PROOF. First, we show that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tau^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1 = \frac{1 + \sqrt{4q-3}}{2}, \quad (1)$$

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \sigma^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1 = \frac{1 - \sqrt{4q-3}}{2}. \quad (2)$$

Let

$$J_q = \left[\frac{1 - \sqrt{4q-3}}{2}, \frac{1 + \sqrt{4q-3}}{2} \right]$$

We start with (1). By Lemma 3.4, the infinite sequence $\boldsymbol{\kappa}_1, \tau(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1, \tau^2(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1, \dots$ is increasing and bounded, and hence it has a limit $\alpha \in J_q$. Consequently, the sequence is also a Cauchy sequence, i.e.,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tau^{k+1}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1 - \tau^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1 = 0.$$

Consider the function $f : J_q \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ where

$$f(x) = \frac{q-1+x(1-x)}{x}.$$

Observe that f is non-negative, continuous, and $f(x) = 0$ iff $x = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{4q-3}}{2}$. Furthermore, for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we have that

$$\tau^{k+1}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1 - \tau^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1 = f(\tau^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1).$$

Hence,

$$0 = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tau^{k+1}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1 - \tau^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1 = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} f(\tau^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1) = f(\alpha)$$

which implies $\alpha = \frac{1 + \sqrt{4q-3}}{2}$ (recall that $\boldsymbol{\kappa}_1 > \frac{1 - \sqrt{4q-3}}{2}$ and the sequence $\boldsymbol{\kappa}_1, \tau(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1, \tau^2(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1, \dots$ is increasing). Equality (2) is proven similarly.

Let $\mathbf{u} \in W \setminus \text{Area}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$. Due to Equalities (1) and (2), there exists $\mathbf{w} \in \text{Points}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ such that $\mathbf{w}_1 \leq \mathbf{u}_1 < \tau(\mathbf{w})_1$. We show that there exists $\mathbf{z} \in W$ such that $\mathbf{z}_1 = \mathbf{w}_1$ and $\mathbf{u} \in L(\mathbf{z})$. This is all we need to prove our lemma, because $\mathbf{w} \in \text{Points}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ implies that $\mathbf{w} = \tau^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ or $\mathbf{w} = \sigma^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$, hence $\sigma^k(\mathbf{z})$ or $\tau^k(\mathbf{z})$ is the $\boldsymbol{\mu}[\mathbf{u}]$ with the required properties, respectively.

To construct \mathbf{z} , we put $\mathbf{z}_1 = \mathbf{w}_1$ and choose \mathbf{z}_2 so that

$$\text{slope}(\mathbf{z}, \tau(\mathbf{z})) = \text{slope}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{u}).$$

Hence, we require that

$$\frac{\mathbf{z}_2(1-\mathbf{z}_1)}{q-1+\mathbf{z}_1(1-\mathbf{z}_1)} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_2-\mathbf{z}_2}{\mathbf{u}_1-\mathbf{z}_1}.$$

From this, we obtain

$$\mathbf{z}_2 = \frac{\mathbf{u}_2(q-1+\mathbf{z}_1(1-\mathbf{z}_1))}{\mathbf{u}_1-\mathbf{z}_1+q-1+\mathbf{z}_1(1-\mathbf{z}_1)}$$

and the proof is finished. \square

LEMMA 3.8. For all $\mathbf{w} \in W$ and $\mathbf{u} \in L(\mathbf{w})$, we have that $\tau(\mathbf{u}) \in L(\tau(\mathbf{w}))$.

PROOF. It is easy to verify that for all $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in W$ and all $\lambda \in (0, 1]$ we have that $\tau(\lambda\mathbf{x} + (1-\lambda)\mathbf{y}) = \lambda'\tau(\mathbf{x}) + (1-\lambda')\tau(\mathbf{y})$ where

$$\lambda' = \frac{\lambda\mathbf{x}_1}{\lambda\mathbf{x}_1 + (1-\lambda)\mathbf{y}_1}$$

Observe that $\lambda' \in (0, 1]$. The lemma follows by putting $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{w}$, $\mathbf{y} = \tau(\mathbf{w})$ and choosing λ so that $\mathbf{u} = \lambda\mathbf{w} + (1-\lambda)\tau(\mathbf{w})$. \square

Now we prove the main result of this section. The symbols q and $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ still refer to the constants fixed in Section 3.1.

THEOREM 3.9. *Let T be a subset of states of some finite-state Markov chain with transition function P such that for every $t \in T$, we have that $\mathbf{v}[t] \in W$ and if $\mathbf{v}[t] \neq \boldsymbol{\kappa}$, then $A_t \subseteq T$ and the following equations are satisfied:*

$$q = 1 - \mathbf{v}[t]_1 + \sum_{u \in A_t} P(t, u) \cdot \mathbf{v}[u]_1 \quad (3)$$

$$q = 1 - \mathbf{v}[t]_1 - \mathbf{v}[t]_2 + \sum_{u \in A_t} P(t, u) \cdot (\mathbf{v}[u]_1 + \mathbf{v}[u]_2) \quad (4)$$

Then $\mathbf{v}[t] \in \text{Area}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ for every $t \in T$. Furthermore, for every $t \in T$ such that $\mathbf{v}[t] \neq \boldsymbol{\kappa}$ and every $u \in A_t$, we have that $\mathbf{v}[u] = \tau(\mathbf{v}[t])$.

PROOF. We start by proving the following claim: for every $t \in T$ such that $\mathbf{v}[t] \neq \boldsymbol{\kappa}$, the vector $\tau(\mathbf{v}[t])$ is a positive convex combination of the vectors in $\{\mathbf{v}[u] \mid u \in A_t\}$.

By rewriting (3), we obtain

$$\frac{q - 1 + \mathbf{v}[t]_1}{\mathbf{v}[t]_1} = \sum_{u \in A_t} \frac{P(t, u)}{\mathbf{v}[t]_1} \mathbf{v}[u]_1 \quad (5)$$

Note that the left-hand side of (5) is equal to $\tau(\mathbf{v}[t])_1$. Furthermore, by simplifying the right-hand side of (4) using (3), we obtain

$$q = q - \mathbf{v}[t]_2 + \sum_{u \in A_t} P(t, u) \cdot \mathbf{v}[u]_2 \quad (6)$$

Thus,

$$\frac{\mathbf{v}[t]_2}{\mathbf{v}[t]_1} = \sum_{u \in A_t} \frac{P(t, u)}{\mathbf{v}[t]_1} \cdot \mathbf{v}[u]_2 \quad (7)$$

Note that the left-hand side of (7) is equal to $\tau(\mathbf{v}[t])_2$. By combining (5) and (7), we have that

$$\tau(\mathbf{v}[t]) = \sum_{u \in A_t} \frac{P(t, u)}{\mathbf{v}[t]_1} \cdot \mathbf{v}[u] \quad (8)$$

which proves the claim.

Now we prove the first part of the theorem, i.e., $\mathbf{v}[t] \in \text{Area}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ for every $t \in T$. Suppose the converse, i.e., the set Out consisting of all $t \in T$ such that $\mathbf{v}[t] \notin \text{Area}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ is non-empty. Note that $\mathbf{v}[t] \neq \boldsymbol{\kappa}$ for every $t \in \text{Out}$. Recall Lemma 3.7, and consider the set $\mu\text{-Out}$ consisting of all $\boldsymbol{\mu}[\mathbf{v}[t]]$ where $t \in \text{Out}$. Let $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ be the vector of $\mu\text{-Out}$ with the smallest second component ($\boldsymbol{\mu}$ exists because Out is finite). Now consider the set of all states of Out whose characteristic vectors belong to $\text{Lines}(\boldsymbol{\mu})$, and select a state z in this set so that $\mathbf{v}[z]_1$ is maximal. Then $\mathbf{v}[u] \in \text{Area}(\boldsymbol{\mu})$ for all $u \in A_z$ (if we assume $\mathbf{v}[u] \notin \text{Area}(\boldsymbol{\mu})$ for some $u \in A_z$, then u is a state of Out such that $\boldsymbol{\mu}[\mathbf{v}[u]] < \boldsymbol{\mu}$, which is a contradiction).

Since $\mathbf{v}[z] \in \text{Lines}(\boldsymbol{\mu})$, there is $\boldsymbol{w} \in \text{Points}(\boldsymbol{\mu})$ such that $\mathbf{v}[z] \in L(\boldsymbol{w})$. By Lemma 3.8, we obtain $\tau(\mathbf{v}[z]) \in L(\tau(\boldsymbol{w}))$. By applying the above claim, we have that $\tau(\mathbf{v}[z])$ is a positive convex combination of the vectors in $\{\mathbf{v}[u] \mid u \in A_z\}$. Since all of these vectors belong to $\text{Area}(\boldsymbol{\mu})$, we can apply Lemma 3.6.B. and conclude that $\mathbf{v}[u] \in L(\tau(\boldsymbol{w})) \cup \{\tau(\boldsymbol{w})\}$ for all $u \in A_z$. Hence, $\mathbf{v}[u] \in \text{Lines}(\boldsymbol{\mu})$ and $\mathbf{v}[u]_1 > \mathbf{v}[z]_1$ for all $u \in A_z$ (see Lemma 3.4), which is a contradiction.

The second part of the theorem follows easily. Let $t \in T$ such that $\mathbf{v}[t] \neq \boldsymbol{\kappa}$. By the above claim, $\tau(\mathbf{v}[t])$ is a positive convex combination of the vectors in $\{\mathbf{v}[u] \mid u \in A_t\}$ and all of these vectors belong to $\text{Area}(\boldsymbol{\mu})$ by the first part of the theorem. Hence, $\mathbf{v}[u] = \tau(\mathbf{v}[t])$ for all $u \in A_t$ by applying Lemma 3.6.A. \square

3.4 A Proof of Theorem 3.1

For a given $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $c = \sigma^n(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1$, $d = \sigma^n(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_2$, and consider the instance $\psi[c, d]$ of $\psi(x, y)$ (note that c, d are rational). We show that $\psi[c, d]$ satisfies the two claims of Theorem 3.1.

To prove the first claim, let us fix a finite-state Markov chain $M = (S, P, v)$ such that $s \models \psi[c, d]$ for some $s \in S$. We show that S contains at least n states. Without restrictions, we assume that all states of S are reachable from s .

Recall that M satisfies all observations formulated in Section 3.2. Let $T \subseteq S$ be the set of all transient and final states of M . We show that T satisfies the assumptions of Theorem 3.9. This is where we use the formula Eq_i , which explains its purpose.

For every final state t we have that $t \models \text{Zero}$, and hence $\mathbf{v}[t] = \boldsymbol{\kappa}$. Now let t be a transient state, and let $A_t = \{u_1, \dots, u_k\}$. Since every u_i is a transient or final state, we have that $A_t \subseteq T$. Furthermore,

$$t \models \langle a, r_i \rangle \wedge \text{Suc}_i \wedge \text{Interval} \wedge Eq_i$$

for precisely one $i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}$. Since $t \models \text{Interval}$, we obtain $\mathbf{v}[t] \in W$. Now consider the formula

$$Eq_i \equiv \mathbf{F}_{=q}^2 S^2(r_i) \wedge \mathbf{F}_{=q}^2 ((S^2(r_i) \wedge \neg b) \vee (S^3(r_i) \wedge b))$$

The first conjunct says that the probability of all runs initiated in t satisfying the path formula $\mathbf{F}^2 S^2(r_i)$ is equal to q . By inspecting the structure of transient states enforced by Suc_i (see Fig. 2), we obtain

$$q = 1 - \mathbf{v}[t]_1 + \sum_{j=1}^k P(t, u_j) \cdot \mathbf{v}[u_j]_1.$$

The second conjunct of Eq_i says that the probability of satisfying $\mathbf{F}^2((S^2(r_i) \wedge \neg b) \vee (S^3(r_i) \wedge b))$ in t is equal to q . Thus, we obtain

$$q = 1 - \mathbf{v}[t]_1 - \mathbf{v}[t]_2 + \sum_{j=1}^k P(t, u_j) \cdot (\mathbf{v}[u_j]_1 + \mathbf{v}[u_j]_2).$$

Since $s \models \psi[c, d]$, we have that s is a transient state satisfying $\mathbf{v}[s] = \sigma^n(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$. By applying Theorem 3.9, we obtain that if t is a transient state satisfying $\mathbf{v}[t] = \sigma^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ where $1 \leq k \leq n$, then every $u \in A_t$ satisfies $\mathbf{v}[u] = \tau(\sigma^k(\boldsymbol{\kappa})) = \sigma^{k-1}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$. Consequently, for every $i \in \{0, \dots, n\}$, there must be a state of S with characteristic vector $\sigma^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$, and these states must be pairwise different (see Lemma 3.4).

To prove the second claim of Theorem 3.1, realize that $\psi[c, d]$ has a model with states $t_0, \dots, t_n, b_0, \dots, b_{n-1}, c_0, \dots, c_{n-1}$ where

- for all $1 \leq i \leq n$, $t_i \models \langle a, r_j \rangle$ where $j = (n-i) \bmod 5$;
- $t_0 \models \langle h, a, r_j \rangle$ where $j = n \bmod 5$;
- for all $1 \leq i \leq n$, we have that $b_{i-1} \models \langle h, b, S^2(r_j) \rangle$ and $c_{i-1} \models \langle h, c, S^2(r_j) \rangle$ where $j = (n-i) \bmod 5$;
- for all $0 \leq i \leq n-1$, we have that $P(b_i, b_i) = P(c_i, c_i) = 1$;
- for all $1 \leq i \leq n$, we have that $P(t_i, t_{i-1}) = \sigma^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1$, $P(t_i, b_{i-1}) = \sigma^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_2$, and $P(t_i, c_{i-1}) = 1 - \sigma^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_1 - \sigma^i(\boldsymbol{\kappa})_2$;
- $P(t_0, t_0) = 1$.

It is easy to check that $t_n \models \psi[c, d]$.

4 SIMULATING MINSKY MACHINES WITH ONE COUNTER

In this section, we prove the following theorem:

Figure 2: The structure of transient states in a model of $\psi[c, d]$

THEOREM 4.1. *Let \mathcal{M} be a one-counter Minsky machine without Halt. Then there is an effectively constructible PCTL formula ψ such that \mathcal{M} is bounded iff ψ is finite-satisfiable.*

For the rest of this section, we fix the following one-counter Minsky machine \mathcal{M} without Halt, where the counter is initialized to zero (see Section 2.3):

$$1 : \text{Ins}_1; \dots m : \text{Ins}_m;$$

Furthermore, we fix q, I_q , and κ in the same way as in Section 3, but we additionally require that $\kappa_1 + \kappa_2 < q - \frac{1}{2}$. Finally, we fix a rational constant γ such that $(1-q)\kappa_2 < \gamma < \frac{3}{4}q - \frac{5}{4}q + \frac{1}{2}q^2$. For example, we can put $q = \frac{13}{16}$, $\kappa = (\frac{17}{64}, \frac{1}{32})$, and $\gamma = 0.06$. These additional assumptions are used in the proofs of Proposition 4.3 and Proposition 5.4.

Intuitively, the counter values $0, 1, 2, \dots$ are represented by characteristic vectors $\kappa, \sigma(\kappa), \sigma^2(\kappa), \dots$. Hence, decrementing and incrementing the counter corresponds to performing the functions τ and σ , respectively. Testing the counter for zero poses no issue because both components of κ are rational and can be directly used as probability constraints. The function τ is implemented in the same way as in the parameterized formula $\psi(x, y)$ constructed in Section 3. Consequently, some subformulae of $\psi(x, y)$ are used in ψ , possibly after small adjustments. The main challenge is to implement the function σ and orchestrate everything so that Theorem 3.9 is still applicable.

4.1 Constructing ψ

The formula ψ uses the same atomic propositions as the parameterized formula $\psi(x, y)$ constructed in Section 3. In addition, ψ employs a set $\text{Labels} = \{\ell_i \mid 1 \leq i \leq m\}$ of fresh propositions modeling the control of \mathcal{M} , and two fresh auxiliary propositions d, e used for implementing the function σ . That is, the set of atomic propositions occurring in ψ is $\mathcal{A} = A \cup \{d, e\} \cup \text{Labels}$. For every $B \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, we use $\langle B \rangle$ to denote the formula $\bigwedge_{p \in B} p \wedge \bigwedge_{p \in \mathcal{A} \setminus B} \neg p$. The intuitive meaning of $\langle B \rangle$ is the same as of $\langle B \rangle$ defined in Section 3.1. The only difference is that the set A is replaced with the richer set \mathcal{A} .

The structure of ψ closely resembles the structure of $\psi(x, y)$, and the overall intuition behind the subformulae stays essentially the

same. We use the same identifiers for denoting adjusted versions of subformulae defined in Section 3.1. If a subformula does not require any adjustment *except for replacing every occurrence of $\langle \cdot \rangle$ with $\langle \cdot \rangle$* , then we re-use this formula and write its identifier in **boldface**. For example, \mathbf{FSuc}_i denotes the formula

$$\mathbf{X}_{=1}(\langle h, a, S(r_i) \rangle \vee \langle h, b, S^2(r_i) \rangle \vee \langle h, c, S^2(r_i) \rangle).$$

We put

$$\psi \equiv \text{Init} \wedge \mathbf{G}_{=1} \text{Invariant}$$

where

$$\text{Init} \equiv \langle a, r_0, \ell_1 \rangle \wedge \mathbf{Zero}$$

$$\text{Invariant} \equiv \mathbf{Fin} \vee \text{Transient} \vee \mathbf{Free}$$

Furthermore, we put

$$\text{Transient} \equiv \mathbf{Trans} \vee \mathbf{CTrans} \vee \mathbf{LTrans}.$$

As we shall see, every transient state t satisfies precisely one of the formulae $\langle a, r_i \rangle, c \wedge r_i \wedge \neg h$, or $\langle x, r_i, \ell \rangle$, where $i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}$, $\ell \in \text{Labels}$, and $x \in \{a, b\}$. The formulae \mathbf{Trans} , \mathbf{CTrans} , and \mathbf{LTrans} define the properties of t in the three respective cases. We define

$$\mathbf{CTrans} \equiv \bigvee_{i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}} c \wedge r_i \wedge \neg h \wedge \mathbf{CSuc}_i \wedge \mathbf{Interval} \wedge \mathbf{Eq}_i$$

where

$$\mathbf{CSuc}_i \equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1}(\langle a, S(r_i) \rangle \vee \langle h, b, S^2(r_i) \rangle \vee \langle h, c, S^2(r_i) \rangle \vee \langle h, c, S^2(r_i), d \rangle)$$

Furthermore, we define

$$\mathbf{LTrans} \equiv \bigvee_{i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}} \bigvee_{\ell \in \text{Labels}} \bigvee_{x \in \{a, b\}} (\langle x, r_i, \ell \rangle \wedge \text{Step}_{i, \ell})$$

where the formula $\text{Step}_{i, \ell}$ is constructed as follows. Let Ins_j be the instruction associated with ℓ , i.e., $\ell = \ell_j$. We distinguish two cases.

(A) If $\text{Ins}_j \equiv \text{if } c=0 \text{ then goto } u \text{ else dec } c; \text{ goto } u'$, then

$$\text{Step}_{i, \ell} \equiv (\mathbf{Zero} \Rightarrow (\mathbf{ZSuc}_{i, \ell} \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1}(b \Rightarrow \mathbf{Zero}))) \wedge (\neg \mathbf{Zero} \Rightarrow (\mathbf{PSuc}_{i, \ell} \wedge \mathbf{Interval} \wedge \mathbf{Eq}_i))$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} ZSuc_{i,\ell} &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1} (\langle\langle h, a, S(r_i) \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle b, S^2(r_i), \ell_u \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle h, c, S^2(r_i) \rangle\rangle \\ &\quad \vee \langle\langle h, c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle) \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1-q} \langle\langle h, c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle \\ PSuc_{i,\ell} &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1} (\langle\langle a, S(r_i), \ell_u \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle h, b, S^2(r_i) \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle h, c, S^2(r_i) \rangle\rangle \\ &\quad \vee \langle\langle h, c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle) \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1-q} \langle\langle h, c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle \end{aligned}$$

(B) If $Ins_j \equiv inc\ c; goto\ u$, then

$$\begin{aligned} Step_{i,\ell} &\equiv (\mathbf{Zero} \Rightarrow ISuc_{i,\ell}) \\ &\quad \wedge (\neg \mathbf{Zero} \Rightarrow (IPSuc_{i,\ell} \wedge \mathbf{Interval} \wedge \mathbf{Eq}_i)) \\ &\quad \wedge \mathbf{F}_{=1-q}^2 (a \wedge S^3(r_i)) \\ &\quad \wedge \mathbf{F}_{=y}^2 ((b \wedge S^4(r_i)) \vee d) \\ &\quad \wedge \mathbf{F}_{=y}^2 ((c \wedge S^4(r_i) \wedge e) \vee d) \end{aligned}$$

where y is the constant fixed at the beginning of Section 4 and

$$\begin{aligned} ISuc_{i,\ell} &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1} (\langle\langle h, a, S(r_i) \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle b, S^2(r_i), \ell_u \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i) \rangle\rangle \\ &\quad \vee \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle) \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1-q} \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle \\ IPSuc_{i,\ell} &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1} (\langle\langle a, S(r_i) \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle b, S^2(r_i), \ell_u \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i) \rangle\rangle \\ &\quad \vee \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle) \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1-q} \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle \end{aligned}$$

This completes the construction of ψ .

Intuitively, if $t \models \langle\langle x, r_i, \ell_j \rangle\rangle$ and $\mathbf{v}[t]$ encodes the current counter value, then $Step_{i,\ell_j}$ enforces the simulation of Ins_j . More concretely,

- if $Ins_j \equiv if\ c=0\ then\ goto\ u\ else\ dec\ c; goto\ u'$, then
 - if $\mathbf{v}[t] = \kappa$ encodes zero, then all $t' \in B_t$ satisfy ℓ_u and $\mathbf{v}[t'] = \kappa$. The simulation continues in the states of B_t .
 - if $\mathbf{v}[t]$ encodes a positive value, then all $t' \in A_t$ satisfy $\ell_{u'}$ and $\mathbf{v}[t'] = \tau(\mathbf{v}[t])$. The counter is decremented, and the simulation continues in the states of A_t .
- If $Ins_j \equiv inc\ c; goto\ u$, then all $t' \in B_t$ satisfy ℓ_u . Furthermore, $\mathbf{v}[t'] = \sigma(\mathbf{v}[t])$ for all $t' \in B_t \cup C_t$ (this part is tricky). The counter is incremented and the simulation continues in the states of B_t .

Furthermore, all transient states t such that $\mathbf{v}[t] \neq \kappa$ satisfy the formula $\mathbf{Interval} \wedge \mathbf{Eq}_i$ (for an appropriate i) so that the conditions of Theorem 3.9 are fulfilled for the set of all transient states.

4.2 A Proof of Theorem 4.1

Recall the one-counter Minsky machine \mathcal{M} without $Halt$ fixed at the beginning of Section 4. Theorem 4.1 is a consequence of the following propositions:

PROPOSITION 4.2. *Let $M = (S, P, v)$ be a finite-state model of ψ . Then for every reachable configuration (j, n) of \mathcal{M} , there exists a state $t \in S$ such that $t \models \ell_j$ and $\mathbf{v}[t] = \sigma^n(\kappa)$.*

PROPOSITION 4.3. *If \mathcal{M} is bounded, then ψ has a finite-state model.*

Note that Proposition 4.2 implies that if \mathcal{M} is not bounded, then the formula ψ does not have a finite-state model.

4.2.1 A Proof of Proposition 4.2. Let us fix a finite-state Markov chain $M = (S, P, v)$ such that $s \models \psi$ for some $s \in S$ and every state of S is reachable from s . Let T be the set of all transient or final states of M . One can easily verify that the conditions of Theorem 3.9 are satisfied for T by inspecting the structure of transient states

similarly as in Section 3.4 (in particular, the formula \mathbf{Eq}_i still implies Equalities (3) and (4)). Thus, by applying Theorem 3.9, we obtain the following observations:

- For every $t \in T$, we have that $\mathbf{v}[t] \in Area(\kappa)$.
- For every $t \in T$ where $\mathbf{v}[t] \neq \kappa$ and every $t' \in A_t$, we have that $\mathbf{v}[t'] = \tau(\mathbf{v}[t])$.

We prove that for every reachable configuration (j, n) of \mathcal{M} , there exists a state $t \in S$ such that $\mathbf{v}[t] = \sigma^n(\kappa)$ and $t \models \langle\langle x, r_i, \ell_j \rangle\rangle$ for some $x \in \{a, b\}$ and $i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}$.

For the initial configuration $(1, 0)$ of \mathcal{M} , we put $t = s$. Since $s \models Init$, we have that $t \models \langle\langle a, r_0, \ell_1 \rangle\rangle$ and $\mathbf{v}[s] = \kappa$ as required. Now we show that if the claim holds for a reachable configuration (j, n) , then it also holds for the configuration (j', n') such that $(j, n) \mapsto (j', n')$.

So, let us fix a reachable configuration (j, n) of \mathcal{M} and a state $t \in S$ such that $\mathbf{v}[t] = \sigma^n(\kappa)$ and $t \models \langle\langle x, r_i, \ell_j \rangle\rangle$ for some $x \in \{a, b\}$ and $i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}$. Since t is reachable from s , we have that $t \models Invariant$, which implies $t \models LTrans$ and hence also $t \models Step_{i,\ell_j}$. We distinguish two cases.

(A) $Ins_j \equiv if\ c=0\ then\ goto\ u\ else\ dec\ c; goto\ u'$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} Step_{i,\ell} &\equiv (\mathbf{Zero} \Rightarrow (ZSuc_{i,\ell} \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1}(b \Rightarrow \mathbf{Zero}))) \\ &\quad \wedge (\neg \mathbf{Zero} \Rightarrow (PSuc_{i,\ell} \wedge \mathbf{Interval} \wedge \mathbf{Eq}_i)) \end{aligned}$$

and there are two subcases.

- $n = 0$. Then $(j', n') = (u, 0)$. Since $\mathbf{v}[t] = \sigma^n(\kappa)$, we obtain $t \models \mathbf{Zero}$. Hence, $t \models ZSuc_{i,\ell} \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1}(b \Rightarrow \mathbf{Zero})$. This implies that every $t' \in B_t$ satisfies $t' \models \langle\langle b, S^2(r_i), \ell_u \rangle\rangle \wedge \mathbf{Zero}$ (hence, $\mathbf{v}[t'] = \kappa$). Since $\mathbf{v}[t]_2 = \kappa_2 > 0$, we have $B_t \neq \emptyset$, and hence at least one such t' exists.
- $n > 0$. Then $(j', n') = (u', n-1)$. Since $\mathbf{v}[t] = \sigma^n(\kappa)$, we obtain $t \models \neg \mathbf{Zero}$ and hence $t \models PSuc_{i,\ell} \wedge \mathbf{Interval} \wedge \mathbf{Eq}_i$. The formula $PSuc_{i,\ell}$ ensures that every $t' \in A_t$ satisfies $t' \models \langle\langle a, S(r_i), \ell_{u'} \rangle\rangle$, and at least one such t' must exist because $\mathbf{v}[t]_1 = \sigma^n(\kappa)_1 > 0$. Furthermore, we have that $\mathbf{v}[t'] = \tau(\sigma^n(\kappa)) = \sigma^{n-1}(\kappa)$ by Observation II. above.

(B) $Ins_j \equiv inc\ c; goto\ u$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} Step_{i,\ell} &\equiv (\mathbf{Zero} \Rightarrow ISuc_{i,\ell}) \\ &\quad \wedge (\neg \mathbf{Zero} \Rightarrow (IPSuc_{i,\ell} \wedge \mathbf{Interval} \wedge \mathbf{Eq}_i)) \\ &\quad \wedge \mathbf{F}_{=1-q}^2 (a \wedge S^3(r_i)) \\ &\quad \wedge \mathbf{F}_{=y}^2 ((b \wedge S^4(r_i)) \vee d) \\ &\quad \wedge \mathbf{F}_{=y}^2 ((c \wedge S^4(r_i) \wedge e) \vee d) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} ISuc_{i,\ell} &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1} (\langle\langle h, a, S(r_i) \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle b, S^2(r_i), \ell_u \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i) \rangle\rangle \\ &\quad \vee \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle) \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1-q} \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle \\ IPSuc_{i,\ell} &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1} (\langle\langle a, S(r_i) \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle b, S^2(r_i), \ell_u \rangle\rangle \vee \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i) \rangle\rangle \\ &\quad \vee \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle) \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1-q} \langle\langle c, S^2(r_i), e \rangle\rangle \end{aligned}$$

The structure of immediate successors of t enforced by this formula is shown in Fig. 3. The formulae $ISuc_{i,\ell}$ and $IPSuc_{i,\ell}$ ensure that $t' \models \langle\langle b, S^2(r_i), u \rangle\rangle$ for every $t' \in B_t$. We show that $\mathbf{v}[t'] = \sigma(\mathbf{v}[t])$ for all $t' \in B_t \cup C_t$.

Due to Observation I above and Lemma 3.6.A, it suffices to prove that $\sigma(\mathbf{v}[t])$ is a positive convex combination of the vectors in

Figure 3: The structure of transient states satisfying $\langle\langle x, r_i, \ell_j \rangle\rangle$ where $x \in \{a, b\}$ and $\text{Ins}_j \equiv \text{inc } c; \text{ goto } u$

$\{\mathbf{v}[t'] \mid t' \in B_t \cup C_t\}$. For a path formula Φ , we use $R[\Phi]$ to denote the set of all $w \in \text{Run}(t)$ such that $w \models \Phi$.

Since $t \models \mathbf{F}_{=1-q}^2(a \wedge S^3(r_i))$, we have $\mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(a \wedge S^3(r_i))]) = 1-q$. By inspecting the structure of immediate successors of t (see Fig. 3), we obtain

$$1-q = \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(a \wedge S^3(r_i))]) = \sum_{t' \in B_t \cup C_t} P(t, t') \cdot \mathbf{v}[t']_1. \quad (9)$$

Observe that $\sum_{t' \in B_t \cup C_t} P(t, t') = 1 - \mathbf{v}[t]_1$. Hence, (9) implies

$$\frac{1-q}{1-\mathbf{v}[t]_1} = \sum_{t' \in B_t \cup C_t} \frac{P(t, t')}{1-\mathbf{v}[t]_1} \cdot \mathbf{v}[t']_1. \quad (10)$$

Note that the left-hand side of (10) is equal to $\sigma(\mathbf{v}[t])_1$.

Furthermore, $t \models \mathbf{F}_{=q}^2((b \wedge S^4(r_i)) \vee d)$. By inspecting the structure of immediate successors of t (see Fig. 3), we obtain⁴

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2((b \wedge S^4(r_i)) \vee d)]) \\ &= \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(b \wedge S^4(r_i))] \cup R[\mathbf{F}^2(d)]) \\ &= \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(b \wedge S^4(r_i))]) + \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(d)]) \\ &= \sum_{t' \in B_t \cup C_t} P(t, t') \cdot \mathbf{v}[t']_2 + \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(d)]) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Similarly, $t \models \mathbf{F}_{=q}^2((c \wedge S^4(r_i) \wedge e) \vee d)$ implies

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2((c \wedge S^4(r_i) \wedge e) \vee d)]) \\ &= \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(c \wedge S^4(r_i) \wedge e)] \cup R[\mathbf{F}^2(d)]) \\ &= \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(c \wedge S^4(r_i) \wedge e)]) + \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(d)]) \\ &= \sum_{t' \in B_t} P(t, t') \cdot (1-q) + \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(d)]) \\ &= \mathbf{v}[t]_2 \cdot (1-q) + \mathbb{P}_t(R[\mathbf{F}^2(d)]) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Since the right-hand sides of (11) and (12) are equal, we have that

$$\mathbf{v}[t]_2 \cdot (1-q) = \sum_{t' \in B_t \cup C_t} P(t, t') \cdot \mathbf{v}[t']_2$$

Hence,

$$\frac{\mathbf{v}[t]_2 \cdot (1-q)}{1-\mathbf{v}[t]_1} = \sum_{t' \in B_t \cup C_t} \frac{P(t, t')}{1-\mathbf{v}[t]_1} \cdot \mathbf{v}[t']_2 \quad (13)$$

Observe that the left-hand side of (13) is equal to $\sigma(\mathbf{v}[t])_2$. By combining (10) and (13), we finally obtain

$$\sigma(\mathbf{v}[t]) = \sum_{t' \in B_t \cup C_t} \frac{P(t, t')}{1-\mathbf{v}[t]_1} \cdot \mathbf{v}[t'].$$

4.2.2 A Proof of Proposition 4.3. Suppose that \mathcal{M} is bounded. We show that then ψ has a finite-state model $M = (S, P, \mathbf{v})$, where every $t \in S$ is a list of all atomic propositions of \mathcal{A} that are satisfied in t , possibly extended with a single integer representing the current counter value.

⁴Here, by writing $C = A \cup B$ we mean that $C = A \cup B$ and $A \cap B = \emptyset$.

The set S and the transition function P are constructed gradually as follows (note that $v(t)$ is determined implicitly by the list of atomic propositions occurring in t):

- Initially, we put $S = \{(a, r_0, \ell_1, 0)\}$ where the state $(a, r_0, \ell_1, 0)$ is declared as *unprocessed*.
- As long as S contains an unprocessed state t , we define the immediate successors of t together with the value of the transition function, and change the status of t to *processed*. The immediate successors of t that are missing in the current S are automatically inserted into S and declared as unprocessed.

Processing of t depends on the form of t . We distinguish several cases (note that **(A)**–**(D)** cover all possibilities).

(A) $t \equiv (x, r_i, \ell_j, n)$ where $x \in \{a, b\}$. There are two subcases.

(Aa) $Ins_j \equiv \text{if } c=0 \text{ then goto } u \text{ else dec } c; \text{ goto } u'$. If $n = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, (h, a, S(r_i))) &= \kappa_1, \\ P(t, (b, S^2(r_i), \ell_u, 0)) &= \kappa_2, \\ P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i), e)) &= 1-q, \\ P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i))) &= q-\kappa_1-\kappa_2 \end{aligned}$$

If $n > 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, (a, S(r_i), \ell_{u'}, n-1)) &= \sigma^n(\kappa)_1, \\ P(t, (h, b, S^2(r_i))) &= \sigma^n(\kappa)_2, \\ P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i), e)) &= 1-q, \\ P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i))) &= q-\sigma^n(\kappa)_1-\sigma^n(\kappa)_2 \end{aligned}$$

(Ab) $Ins_j \equiv \text{inc } c; \text{ goto } u$. If $n = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, (h, a, S(r_i))) &= \kappa_1, \\ P(t, (b, S^2(r_i), \ell_u, 1)) &= \kappa_2, \\ P(t, (c, S^2(r_i), e, 1)) &= 1-q, \\ P(t, (c, S^2(r_i), 1)) &= q-\kappa_1-\kappa_2 \end{aligned}$$

If $n > 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, (a, S(r_i), n-1)) &= \sigma^n(\kappa)_1, \\ P(t, (b, S^2(r_i), \ell_u, n+1)) &= \sigma^n(\kappa)_2, \\ P(t, (c, S^2(r_i), e, n+1)) &= 1-q, \\ P(t, (c, S^2(r_i), n+1)) &= q-\sigma^n(\kappa)_1-\sigma^n(\kappa)_2 \end{aligned}$$

(B) $t \equiv (a, r_i, n)$. If $n = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, (h, a, S(r_i))) &= \kappa_1, \\ P(t, (h, b, S^2(r_i))) &= \kappa_2, \\ P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i))) &= 1-\kappa_1-\kappa_2 \end{aligned}$$

If $n > 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, (a, S(r_i), n-1)) &= \sigma^n(\kappa)_1, \\ P(t, (h, b, S^2(r_i))) &= \sigma^n(\kappa)_2, \\ P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i))) &= 1-\sigma^n(\kappa)_1-\sigma^n(\kappa)_2 \end{aligned}$$

(C) $t \equiv (c, r_i, n)$ or $t \equiv (c, r_i, e, n)$. Then $n > 0$, and we put

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, (a, S(r_i), n-1)) &= \sigma^n(\kappa)_1, \\ P(t, (h, b, S^2(r_i))) &= \sigma^n(\kappa)_2, \\ P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i), d)) &= p_n, \\ P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i))) &= 1-\sigma^n(\kappa)_1-\sigma^n(\kappa)_2-p_n \end{aligned}$$

where

$$p_n = \frac{\gamma - (1-q)\sigma^{n-1}(\kappa)_2}{1 - \sigma^n(\kappa)_1 - \sigma^n(\kappa)_2}$$

Note that $0 < p_n < 1 - \sigma^n(\kappa)_1 - \sigma^n(\kappa)_2$ due to the constraints imposed on γ and κ at the beginning of Section 4. More precisely, the constraint $\gamma > (1-q)\kappa_2$ ensures that $p_n > 0$, and the constraint $\gamma < \frac{3}{4}q - \frac{5}{4}q + \frac{1}{2}q^2$ ensures that $2p_n < 1 - (2(q-\frac{1}{2}) + (1-q))$ (recall that $\kappa_1 + \kappa_2 < q - \frac{1}{2}$ and $\sigma^m(\kappa)$ is strictly less than κ in both components for every $m \geq 0$). This is more than we need here; the constraints are chosen so that they also satisfy the stronger requirements needed in the proof of Proposition 5.4.

(D) t contains h . Then $P(t, t) = 1$.

Since \mathcal{M} is bounded, the above construction terminates and produces a Markov chain where the number of states is proportional to the number of reachable configurations of \mathcal{M} . It is easy to check that $(a, r_0, \ell_1, 0) \models \psi$ by verifying that every $t \in S$ satisfies either *Fin*, *Transient*, or *Free* (this requires a routine inspection of the states reachable from t in at most two steps). In particular, note that every state of the form (b, r_i, ℓ_j, k) where $Ins_j \equiv \text{inc } c; \text{ goto } u$ satisfies $\mathbf{F}_{=y}^2((b \wedge S^4(r_i)) \vee d)$ and $\mathbf{F}_{=y}^2((c \wedge S^4(r_i) \wedge e) \vee d)$. This is where we need the constant p_n of **(D)**.

It is worth noting that if \mathcal{M} is unbounded, then the infinite-state Markov chain obtained as the least fixed point of the extension operator defined by the above rules is a model of ψ .

5 UNDECIDABILITY OF FINITE SATISFIABILITY FOR PCTL

In this section, we prove the main result of this paper, i.e., the undecidability of the finite satisfiability problem for the logic PCTL. Technically, the result is obtained by reducing the boundedness problem for synchronized products of one-counter Minsky machines without *Halt* defined in the next paragraph.

Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}_1 &\equiv 1 : Ins_1^1; \dots m : Ins_m^1; \\ \mathcal{M}_2 &\equiv 1 : Ins_1^2; \dots m : Ins_m^2; \end{aligned}$$

be one-counter Minsky machines without *Halt* and $I = (I_1, I_2)$ a partition of $\{1, \dots, m\}$, i.e., $I_1 \cup I_2 = \{1, \dots, m\}$ and $I_1 \cap I_2 = \emptyset$. An *I-synchronized product* of $\mathcal{M}_1, \mathcal{M}_2$, denoted by $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$, is a computational device⁵ operating over two counters in the following way.

A *configuration* of $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ is a triple (j, n_1, n_2) where $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and $n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}$ are counter values. For every configuration (j, n_1, n_2) of $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$, the *successor configuration* (j', n'_1, n'_2) is determined as follows (recall that \mapsto denotes the “standard” computational step of a Minsky machine, see Section 2.3):

⁵ $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ is a non-standard computational model introduced specifically for purposes of this paper. Encoding the computation of $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ by a PCTL formula is substantially easier than encoding the computation of a two-counter Minsky machine.

- If $j \in I_1$, then j', n'_1, n'_2 are the unique integers satisfying $(j, n_1) \mapsto (j', n'_1)$ in \mathcal{M}_1 and $(j, n_2) \mapsto (j'', n'_2)$ in \mathcal{M}_2 (for some $j'' \in \{1, \dots, m\}$).
- If $j \in I_2$, then j', n'_1, n'_2 are the unique integers satisfying $(j, n_1) \mapsto (j'', n'_1)$ in \mathcal{M}_1 and $(j, n_2) \mapsto (j', n'_2)$ in \mathcal{M}_2 (for some $j'' \in \{1, \dots, m\}$).

In other words, $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ simultaneously executes the instructions Ins_j^1 and Ins_j^2 operating on the first and the second counter, and the next j' is determined by either Ins_j^1 or Ins_j^2 , depending on whether $j \in I_1$ or $j \in I_2$, respectively.

We write $(j, n_1, n_2) \rightsquigarrow (j', n'_1, n'_2)$ when (j', n'_1, n'_2) is a successor of (j, n_1, n_2) . A configuration of (j, n_1, n_2) of $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ is *reachable* if $(1, 0, 0) \rightsquigarrow^* (j, n_1, n_2)$, where \rightsquigarrow^* is the reflexive and transitive closure of \rightsquigarrow . We say that $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ is *bounded* if there is $b \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $n_1, n_2 \leq b$ for every reachable configuration (j, n_1, n_2) .

Let \mathcal{M} be a two-counter Minsky machine without *Halt*. The machine \mathcal{M} can be faithfully simulated by an effectively constructible synchronized product $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ of two one-counter Minsky machines without *Halt*. Intuitively, $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ simulates \mathcal{M} so that the instructions on c_1 and c_2 are performed by \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 , respectively. As long as \mathcal{M}_1 performs instructions on c_1 , \mathcal{M}_2 keeps incrementing/decrementing c_2 alternately. When an instruction operating on c_2 is reached, the control is passed to \mathcal{M}_2 . Before executing the instruction on c_2 , \mathcal{M}_2 possibly decrements c_2 to restore its value. We refer to [11] for technical details. Thus, we obtain the following:

PROPOSITION 5.1. *The boundedness problem for synchronized products of one-counter Minsky machines without Halt is undecidable.*

Now we formulate and prove the main result of this paper.

THEOREM 5.2. *Let $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ be a synchronized product of one-counter Minsky machines without Halt. Then there is an effectively constructible PCTL formula Ψ such that $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ is bounded iff Ψ is finitely satisfiable.*

For the rest of this section, we fix the following one-counter Minsky machines without *Halt*:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}_1 &\equiv 1 : Ins_1^1; \dots m : Ins_m^1; \\ \mathcal{M}_2 &\equiv 1 : Ins_1^2; \dots m : Ins_m^2; \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, we fix a partition $I = (I_1, I_2)$ of $\{1, \dots, m\}$.

5.1 Constructing Ψ

Roughly speaking, the formula Ψ is obtained by “merging” the formulae ψ_1 and ψ_2 of Section 4 constructed for \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 using disjoint sets of atomic propositions \mathcal{A}^1 and \mathcal{A}^2 . The main modification is in the subformulae $LTrans$ of ψ_1 and ψ_2 , where we need to adjust the way of selecting the propositions of *Labels* passed to the successors so that the operational semantics of $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ is reflected properly. When constructing ψ_1 and ψ_2 , we assume the constants q, κ , and γ satisfy the same constraints as in Section 4 (these constants are used in both ψ_1 and ψ_2).

So, for $k \in \{1, 2\}$, we fix a set $\mathcal{A}^k = \{p^k \mid p \in \mathcal{A}\}$ of atomic propositions so that $\mathcal{A}^1 \cap \mathcal{A}^2 = \emptyset$. The set of atomic propositions used in Ψ is $\mathcal{A}^1 \cup \mathcal{A}^2$. For every formula $Form$ constructed in

Section 4 and $k \in \{1, 2\}$, we use $Form^k$ to denote the formula obtained from $Form$ by replacing all propositions of \mathcal{A} with \mathcal{A}^k . For example, $t \models \langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{r}_i \rangle^1$ if t satisfies both a^1 and r_i^1 , and no other proposition of \mathcal{A}^1 . The formula does not say anything about the validity of the propositions of \mathcal{A}^2 in t .

When we need to define new formulae over \mathcal{A}^1 and \mathcal{A}^2 with the same structure up to the upper indexes of atomic propositions, we write a definition of $Form^k$ parameterized by the k . For example, by stipulating $Form^k \equiv h^k \vee \langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{r}_i \rangle^k$, we simultaneously define $Form^1 \equiv h^1 \vee \langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{r}_i \rangle^1$ and $Form^2 \equiv h^2 \vee \langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{r}_i \rangle^2$. Furthermore, for $k \in \{1, 2\}$, the other element of $\{1, 2\}$ is denoted by k' , i.e., $\{k, k'\} = \{1, 2\}$.

We put

$$\Psi \equiv \mathbf{Init}^1 \wedge \mathbf{Init}^2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_{=1}(\mathbf{Invariant} \wedge \mathbf{LPass})$$

where

$$\mathbf{LPass} \equiv \left(\bigvee_{j=1}^m (\ell_j^1 \wedge \ell_j^2) \right) \Rightarrow \mathbf{x}_{>0} \left(\bigvee_{j=1}^m (\ell_j^1 \wedge \ell_j^2) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Invariant} &\equiv (\mathbf{Fin}^1 \vee \mathbf{Transient}^1 \vee \mathbf{Free}^1) \\ &\wedge (\mathbf{Fin}^2 \vee \mathbf{Transient}^2 \vee \mathbf{Free}^2) \end{aligned}$$

Intuitively, if $t \models \ell_j^1 \wedge \ell_j^2$, then the instructions Ins_j^1 and Ins_j^2 are “simulated in parallel” in t . The formula \mathbf{LPass} enforces the existence of at least one immediate successor t' of t where the successor instructions $Ins_{j'}^1$ and $Ins_{j'}^2$ are again simulated jointly. For all $k \in \{1, 2\}$, we put

$$\mathbf{Transient}^k \equiv \mathbf{Trans}^k \vee \mathbf{CTrans}^k \vee \mathbf{LTrans}^k$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{LTrans}^k &\equiv \left(\bigvee_{j=1}^m (\ell_j^k \wedge \ell_j^{k'}) \right) \Rightarrow \mathbf{Sim}^k \\ &\wedge \left(\bigvee_{j=1}^m \ell_j^k \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^m \neg \ell_j^{k'} \right) \Rightarrow \mathbf{Abandon}^k \end{aligned}$$

As we shall see, for every state t reachable from a state satisfying Ψ we have that $t \models \ell_j^k$ for at most one $\ell_j \in \mathbf{Labels}$. Furthermore, if $t \models \ell_j^1 \wedge \ell_{j'}^2$, then $j = j'$. Intuitively, the formula \mathbf{LTrans}^k says that when $t \models \ell_j^k \wedge \ell_{j'}^{k'}$, we continue with simulating the instruction $Ins_j^{k'}$. If t satisfies a proposition of \mathbf{Labels}^k but no proposition of $\mathbf{Labels}^{k'}$, we “abandon” the simulation. In the latter case, the immediate successors of t must still have an appropriate structure so that no formula is “spoilt” in the immediate predecessor of t . This is enforced by the formula $\mathbf{Abandon}^k$. More precisely, we put

$$\mathbf{Abandon}^k \equiv (\mathbf{Zero}^k \Rightarrow \mathbf{OZer}^k) \wedge (\neg \mathbf{Zero}^k \Rightarrow \mathbf{OPos}^k).$$

The formulae \mathbf{OZer}^k and \mathbf{OPos}^k are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{OZer}^k &\equiv \bigvee_{i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}} (r_i^k \wedge \mathbf{OZSuc}_i^k) \\ \mathbf{OPos}^k &\equiv \bigvee_{i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}} (r_i^k \wedge \mathbf{OPSuc}_i^k \wedge \mathbf{Interval}^k \wedge \mathbf{Eq}_i^k) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} OZSuc_i^k &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1} (\langle \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{r}_i) \rangle^k \vee \langle \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{S}^2(\mathbf{r}_i) \rangle^k \vee \langle \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{S}^2(\mathbf{r}_i) \rangle^k \\ &\quad \vee \langle \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{S}^2(\mathbf{r}_i), \mathbf{e} \rangle^k) \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1-q} \langle \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{S}^2(\mathbf{r}_i), \mathbf{e} \rangle^k \\ OPSuc_i^k &\equiv \mathbf{X}_{=1} (\langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{r}_i) \rangle^k \vee \langle \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{S}^2(\mathbf{r}_i) \rangle^k \vee \langle \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{S}^2(\mathbf{r}_i) \rangle^k \\ &\quad \vee \langle \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{S}^2(\mathbf{r}_i), \mathbf{e} \rangle^k) \wedge \mathbf{X}_{=1-q} \langle \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{S}^2(\mathbf{r}_i), \mathbf{e} \rangle^k \end{aligned}$$

The formulae Sim^k , where $k \in \{1, 2\}$, enforce the simulation of one computational step of $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$. We put

$$Sim^k \equiv \bigvee_{i \in \{0, \dots, 4\}} \bigvee_{\ell \in Labels} \bigvee_{x \in \{a, b\}} (\langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{r}_i, \ell \rangle^k \wedge Step_{i, \ell}^k)$$

where the formula $Step_{i, \ell}^k$ is constructed as follows. Let Ins_j^k be the instruction associated with ℓ , i.e., $\ell = \ell_j$. If $j \in I_k$, then

$$Step_{i, \ell}^k \equiv Step_{i, \ell}^k$$

Now let $j \notin I_k$. For every $u \in Labels$, let $Step_{i, \ell}^k[u]$ be the formula obtained from $Step_{i, \ell}^k$ by substituting every occurrence of every proposition of $Labels^k$ with t_u^k . We distinguish two cases (recall that $k' \neq k$ is “the other index” of $\{1, 2\}$).

(A) $Ins_j^{k'} \equiv \text{if } c=0 \text{ then goto } u \text{ else dec } c; \text{ goto } u'$. Then,

$$Step_{i, \ell}^k \equiv (\mathbf{Zero}^{k'} \Rightarrow Step_{i, \ell}^k[u]) \wedge (\neg \mathbf{Zero}^{k'} \Rightarrow Step_{i, \ell}^k[u'])$$

(B) $Ins_j^{k'} \equiv \text{inc } c; \text{ goto } u$. Then,

$$Step_{i, \ell}^k \equiv Step_{i, \ell}^k[u]$$

This completes the construction of Ψ .

5.2 A Proof of Theorem 5.2

For every state t of some Markov chain and every $k \in \{1, 2\}$, we use $\mathbf{v}^k[t] \in [0, 1]^2$ to denote the k -th characteristic vector of t where

- $\mathbf{v}^k[t]_1$ is the probability of satisfying the path formula $\mathbf{X} a^k$ in the state t ;
- $\mathbf{v}^k[t]_2$ is the probability of satisfying the path formula $\mathbf{X} b^k$ in the state t .

Theorem 5.2 is a consequence of the following propositions.

PROPOSITION 5.3. *Let $M = (S, P, v)$ be a finite-state model of Ψ . Then for every reachable configuration (j, n_1, n_2) of $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$, there is $t \in S$ such that $t \models \ell_j^1 \wedge \ell_j^2$, $\mathbf{v}^1[t] = \sigma^{n_1}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$, and $\mathbf{v}^2[t] = \sigma^{n_2}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$.*

PROPOSITION 5.4. *If $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ is bounded, then Ψ has a finite-state model.*

Propositions 5.3 and 5.4 are proven by reusing the arguments of Propositions 4.2 and 4.3 with some modifications and extensions.

5.2.1 A Proof of Proposition 5.3. Let $M = (S, P, v)$ be a Markov chain such that $s \models \Psi$ for some $s \in S$ and every state of S is reachable from s . For every $k \in \{1, 2\}$, let T^k be the set of all $t \in S$ such that $t \not\models h^k$. It is easy to verify that the conditions of Theorem 3.9 are satisfied for both T^1 and T^2 , where $\mathbf{v}^1[t]$ and $\mathbf{v}^2[t]$ play the role of $\mathbf{v}[t]$, respectively.

We prove that for every reachable configuration (j, n_1, n_2) of $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$, there exists a state $t \in S$ such that $\mathbf{v}^1[t] = \sigma^{n_1}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$,

$\mathbf{v}^2[t] = \sigma^{n_2}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$, and $t \models \langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{r}_i, \ell_j \rangle^1 \wedge \langle \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{r}_i', \ell_j \rangle^2$ for some $x, x' \in \{a, b\}$ and $i, i' \in \{0, \dots, 4\}$.

For the initial configuration $(1, 0, 0)$ of $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$, we put $t = s$. Since $s \models \mathbf{Init}^1 \wedge \mathbf{Init}^2$, we have that $t \models \langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{r}_0, \ell_1 \rangle^1 \wedge \langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{r}_0, \ell_1 \rangle^2$ and $\mathbf{v}^1[s] = \mathbf{v}^2[s] = \boldsymbol{\kappa}$ as required. Now we show that if the claim holds for a reachable configuration (j, n_1, n_2) , then it also holds for the configuration (j', n'_1, n'_2) such that $(j, n_1, n_2) \rightsquigarrow (j', n'_1, n'_2)$.

So, let $t \in S$ be a state such that $t \models \langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{r}_i, \ell_j \rangle^1 \wedge \langle \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{r}_i', \ell_j \rangle^2$, $\mathbf{v}^1[t] = \sigma^{n_1}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$, and $\mathbf{v}^2[t] = \sigma^{n_2}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$. Then, $t \models LTrans^1 \wedge LTrans^2$, which implies $t \models Step_{i, \ell_j}^1 \wedge Step_{i', \ell_j}^2$. By the definition of $Step_{i, \ell}^k$ and the arguments of Proposition 4.2, we obtain that every immediate successor t' of t such that $t' \models \ell_j^1$, satisfies $\mathbf{v}^1[t'] = \sigma^{n'_1}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ and $t' \models \langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{r}_o, \ell_{j'} \rangle^1$ for some $y \in \{a, b\}$ and $o \in \{0, \dots, 4\}$. Furthermore, every immediate successor t'' of t such that $t'' \models \ell_j^2$, satisfies $\mathbf{v}^2[t''] = \sigma^{n'_2}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ and $t'' \models \langle \mathbf{y}', \mathbf{r}_o', \ell_{j'} \rangle^2$ for some $y' \in \{a, b\}$ and $o' \in \{0, \dots, 4\}$. By applying the formula $LPass$, we obtain that there exists a successor of t satisfying all of these conditions simultaneously.

5.2.2 A Proof of Proposition 5.4. If $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ is bounded, then a finite-state model $M = (S, P, v)$ of Ψ can be constructed by extending (and slightly modifying) the procedure described in Section 4.2.2. Now, the states of S are finite lists of atomic propositions contained in $\mathcal{A}^1 \cup \mathcal{A}^2$, possibly extended with at most two integers representing the counter values (the order of these integers is significant; the first/second integer represents the value of the first/second counter, respectively).

Initially, we put $S = \{(a^1, r_0^1, \ell_1^1, a^2, r_0^2, \ell_1^2, 0, 0)\}$ and declare the only state of S *unprocessed*. Similarly as in Section 4.2.2, we define the immediate successors of an unprocessed state $t \in S$, where the successors missing in S are inserted into S and declared as unprocessed. Before defining the processing rules, we introduce some useful notions.

For a given $t \in S$, we construct the lists t_1 and t_2 as follows. Initially, t_1 and t_2 contain all $p \in \mathcal{A}$ where $p^1 \in t$ and $p^2 \in t$, respectively. If $h \notin t_1$, then the first integer occurring in t is appended to t_1 ; and if $h \notin t_2$, then the first or the second integer occurring in t is appended to t_2 , depending on whether $h \in t_1$ or not, respectively (as we shall see, t always contains the adequate number of integers).

Let $v(t_1)$ and $v(t_2)$ be the sets of all immediate successors of t_1 and t_2 obtained by applying the rules (A)–(D) of Section 4.2.2, where the underlying one-counter Minsky machine is \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 , respectively. Observe that for all $k \in \{1, 2\}$, the set $v(t_k)$ satisfies precisely one of the following conditions:

- $v(t_k) = \{t_k\}$. This happens iff $h \in t_k$.
- $v(t_k)$ has precisely three elements, containing propositions a , b , and c , respectively, such that the last element does not contain d or e . These elements are denoted by ta_k , tb_k , and tc_k , respectively.
- $v(t_k)$ has precisely four elements; apart of ta_k , tb_k , and tc_k , there is also the fourth element containing d or e . This fourth element is denoted by tx_k .

For all $t'_1 \in v(t_1)$ and $t'_2 \in v(t_2)$, the *indexed union* of t'_1 and t'_2 , denoted by $t'_1 \uplus t'_2$, is a list containing all propositions p^1 such that $p \in t'_1$, and all propositions p^2 such that $p \in t'_2$. Furthermore, if t'_1 contains an integer, then this integer is appended to $t'_1 \uplus t'_2$; and if

t'_2 contains an integer, then this integer is appended to $t'_1 \uplus t'_2$ (the order of appending the integers is significant).

Now, we define the processing rules. Let $t \in S$ be an unprocessed state. We distinguish several possibilities.

(A) $t_1 \cap t_2$ contains a proposition $\ell_j \in \text{Labels}$. Then, the immediate successors of t are determined as follows. Let $t'_1 \in v(t_1)$ and $t'_2 \in v(t_2)$ be the unique elements such that t'_1 contains $\ell_{j_1} \in \text{Labels}$ and t'_2 contains $\ell_{j_2} \in \text{Labels}$ (note that ℓ_{j_1} and ℓ_{j_2} are not necessarily the same). We put

$$P(t, t') = \min\{P(t_1, t'_1), P(t_2, t'_2)\}$$

where t' is obtained from $t'_1 \uplus t'_2$ by replacing either $t_{j_1}^1$ with $t_{j_2}^1$ or $t_{j_2}^2$ with $t_{j_1}^2$, depending on whether $j \in I_2$ or $j \in I_1$, respectively. Furthermore,

- if $P(t_1, t'_1) > P(t_2, t'_2)$, then

$$P(t, t'_1 \uplus tc_2) = P(t_1, t'_1) - P(t_2, t'_2);$$
- if $P(t_2, t'_2) > P(t_1, t'_1)$, then

$$P(t, tc_1 \uplus t'_2) = P(t_2, t'_2) - P(t_1, t'_1);$$
- for all $t''_1 \in v(t_1)$ such that $t''_1 \neq t'_1$ and $t''_1 \in \{ta_1, tb_1, tx_1\}$,

$$P(t, t''_1 \uplus tc_2) = P(t_1, t''_1);$$
- for all $t''_2 \in v(t_2)$ such that $t''_2 \neq t'_2$ and $t''_2 \in \{ta_2, tb_2, tx_2\}$,

$$P(t, tc_1 \uplus t''_2) = P(t_2, t''_2);$$
- finally, we put $P(t, tc_1 \uplus tc_2) = 1 - s$ where s is the sum of all $P(t, \cdot)$ defined above.

Note that $s < 1$ due to the constraints on q and κ adopted in Section 4.

(B) $t_1 \cap \text{Labels} \neq \emptyset$, $h \notin t_2$, and **(A)** does not apply. Then $t_1 \equiv (\ell_j, y, r_i, n)$ where $y \in \{a, b\}$. We distinguish two subcases.

$n = 0$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, (h, a, S(r_i)) \uplus tc_2) &= \kappa_1, \\ P(t, (h, b, S^2(r_i)) \uplus tc_2) &= \kappa_2, \\ P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i), e) \uplus tc_2) &= 1 - q. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, for every $t''_2 \in \{ta_2, tb_2, tx_2\}$, we put

$$P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i)) \uplus t''_2) = P(t_2, t''_2).$$

Finally, we put $P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i)) \uplus tc_2) = 1 - s$ where s is the sum of all $P(t, \cdot)$ defined above.

$n > 0$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} P(t, (a, S(r_i), n-1) \uplus tc_2) &= \sigma^n(\kappa)_1, \\ P(t, (h, b, S^2(r_i)) \uplus tc_2) &= \sigma^n(\kappa)_2, \\ P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i), e) \uplus tc_2) &= 1 - q. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, for every $t''_2 \in \{ta_2, tb_2, tx_2\}$,

$$P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i)) \uplus t''_2) = P(t_2, t''_2).$$

Finally, we put $P(t, (h, c, S^2(r_i)) \uplus tc_2) = 1 - s$ where s is the sum of all $P(t, \cdot)$ defined above.

(C) $t_2 \cap \text{Labels} \neq \emptyset$, $h \notin t_1$, and **(A)** does not apply. This case is fully symmetric to **(B)**.

(D) $h \notin t_1$, $h \notin t_2$, and the previous cases do not apply. For every $t''_1 \in \{ta_1, tb_1, tx_1\}$,

$$P(t, t''_1 \uplus tc_2) = P(t_1, t''_1).$$

Similarly, for all $t''_2 \in \{ta_2, tb_2, tx_2\}$,

$$P(t, tc_1 \uplus t''_2) = P(t_2, t''_2).$$

Finally, $P(t, tc_1 \uplus tc_2) = 1 - s$, where s is the sum of all $P(t, \cdot)$ above.

(E) $h \notin t_1$ and $h \in t_2$. Then, $P(t, t'_1 \uplus t_2) = P(t_1, t'_1)$ for all $t'_1 \in v(t_1)$.

(F) $h \in t_1$ and $h \notin t_2$. Then, $P(t, t_1 \uplus t'_2) = P(t_2, t'_2)$ for all $t'_2 \in v(t_2)$.

(G) $h \in t_1$ and $h \in t_2$. Then $P(t, t) = 1$.

If $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ is bounded, then the above procedure terminates after finitely many steps. A routine check (similar to the one performed in the proof of Proposition 4.3) reveals that $(a^1, r_0^1, \ell_1^1, a^2, r_0^2, \ell_1^2, 0, 0) \models \Psi$. Observe that if $\mathcal{M}_1 \times_I \mathcal{M}_2$ is unbounded, then the infinite-state Markov chain obtained as the least fixed point of the extension operator defined by the above rules is a model of Ψ .

6 CONCLUSIONS

We have shown that the finite satisfiability problem for PCTL is undecidable. The construction of Theorem 5.2 is applicable also to a universal Minsky machine. Hence, there exists a fixed parameterized PCTL formula such that the finite satisfiability of its instances is undecidable. Furthermore, the undecidability result remains valid even if the set of eligible finite models is restricted to *tree-like* models, where the underlying graph of a Markov chain is a tree with self-loops on all leaves (this requires a slight modification of our construction).

A recent follow-up to this work [11] shows that the *general* PCTL satisfiability problem is even *highly undecidable*, i.e., beyond the arithmetical hierarchy.

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